

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

Annual Report 2009–2010

DIRECTORS, JULY 1, 2009–JUNE 30, 2010

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THE COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES (CLIR) grew out of the 1997 merger of the Commission on Preservation and Access (CPA) and the Council on Library Resources (CLR). Over the years, CPA and CLR, in partnership with libraries, archives, and other information providers, had advocated collaborative approaches to preserving the nation's intellectual heritage and strengthening the many components of its information system. CLIR was founded to continue this tradition of support for a national information system and a seamless web of information resources, of which all libraries and archives are a part.

The convening role is central to CLIR's mission. CLIR brings together experts from around the country and around the world and asks them to turn their intelligence to the problems that libraries, archives, and information organizations face as they integrate digital resources and services into their well-established print-based environments.

CLIR urges individuals to look beyond the immediate challenges and imagine the most desirable outcomes for the users of libraries and archives—to be rigorously practical and to dream.

* Term ended November 2009

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

ANNUAL REPORT 2009–2010

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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Pennsylvania State University, University Libraries
Princeton University Library
Rice University
Stanford University
The University of Tennessee
University of California, Berkeley
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Joint Information Systems Committee (JISC)

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(AS OF JUNE 30, 2010)

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LETTER FROM THE CHAIRMAN

Stephen Nichols
Chairman of the Board

One of the exciting things about chairing CLIR's Board is being close enough to the organization's activities to appreciate their dynamism and diversity, while still being sufficiently removed to perceive CLIR's impact on the broader scholarly community. It is an impressive sight.

The impact of the Digital Library Federation's (DLF's) reintegration with CLIR can already be felt. DLF Program Director Rachel Frick hit the ground running in May and has not slackened pace. The result can be seen in the fact that weeks before the DLF Fall Forum, demand for attendance was so high that registration had to be closed before the deadline. By combining traditional panels and what she terms "dynamic, un-conference opportunities," Rachel has infused the Forum with new energy and innovation. Through the DLF Program, CLIR has also developed a formal affiliation with the Taiga Forum, which held its annual meeting in conjunction with the DLF Fall Forum. With DLF again operating at full throttle, the positive dynamic of the CLIR/DLF configuration is there for all to see. The Board is grateful to CLIR President Chuck Henry and Rachel Frick for their efforts in shaping this configuration.

DLF's reintegration with CLIR is just one aspect of a highly productive year. CLIR published two new reports in 2010: *The Idea of Order: Transforming Research Collections for 21st Century Scholarship* was issued in June, and *The State of Recorded Sound Preservation in the United States: A National Legacy at Risk in the Digital Age* was published in August. A third report, *Digital Forensics and Born-Digital Content in Cultural Heritage Collections*, is due before the end of the year. CLIR reports such as these continue to set the agenda for research and discussions worldwide.

The Hidden Collections Program, funded by The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and launched two years ago, is having a noticeable impact in the scholarly community and has dramatically raised CLIR's visibility among cultural heritage institutions. Outreach to smaller academic institutions likewise expanded this year through CLIR's collaboration with the Council of Independent Colleges on a new joint program to support professional development opportunities for staff at small and midsize private colleges and universities. Finally, CLIR's workshops on undergraduate work practices, initiated in November 2009, are a timely complement to the successful workshops on faculty research behavior begun in 2007.

The following pages provide an overview of the myriad activities CLIR has undertaken this year. Let me simply say, in closing, that it would be difficult to find a staff that produces as many substantive results with so few people as CLIR does under Chuck Henry's leadership. The Board recognizes and appreciates the commitment of CLIR's dedicated professionals.

Stephen Nichols
November 2010

MESSAGE FROM THE PRESIDENT

Charles Henry
President

Historically, CLIR has stood at a nexus of library professionals, information technology experts, research faculty and teachers, and administrators. This has allowed us to delve into complex issues that challenge higher education. In so doing, we have aimed to maintain a balance between highly conceptual research and its practical application. Reports such as *No Brief Candle* and *The Idea of Order* combine theoretical assumptions, rigorous analysis, and applicable recommendations that can help manage and steer our institutions productively.

In last year's message, I noted a flourishing of new partnerships within higher education that, if successful, would create genuine interdependencies: deep collaborations that could redefine our academic environment. In researching these new models of practice, we discovered that the traditional organizational structures of libraries and educational institutions are incompatible with, or in some cases antagonistic to, the digital tools, resources, networks, and virtual clouds upon which we have come to rely.

Universities and colleges often define themselves by exclusivity and singularity of purpose. They compete with each other; they measure themselves against one another; and they hold tightly to their idiosyncrasies as defining elements of their status. There is tension between these inherited conceptual notions of separate, particular, and solitary and today's emerging networked infrastructure of information that has no "place." As currently conceived, neither libraries nor universities are structured, organized, or funded to achieve the kind of federated and collaborative enterprise that the digital environment can provide.

In 2010, we find ourselves in a constellation of academic villages that is redundant and expensive. In light of, and in response to, this reality, CLIR will devote considerable time and talent in the coming years to identifying consortial models that can effectively reduce costs while enhancing the infrastructure and services for scholarship and teaching. Common to these efforts will be developing strong regional coalitions that bring together diverse institutions within a national framework; federating shared resources and interests, including collections, technology, and expertise; and creating a genuine, volitional dependency on other participating institutions for the provision of what was once a locally owned and managed asset.

We are calling these collaborative projects *macro solutions*. From a strategic vantage point, there is no ambiguity: the future of academic libraries and higher education rests on our ability to reconceive ourselves holistically. The various components of scholarly communication—discovering, reconstituting, publishing, and sharing knowledge, and keeping its various manifestations securely preserved and accessible—must be understood as interrelated and interdependent. The inherited norms, customs, traditions, and institutions that have structured research and teaching now need to be constructively challenged, redefined, and reassembled.

Through repositioning, consolidation, and convergence, universities and colleges can help ensure the vitality of higher education and expand its capacity for future discovery without compromising its exactitude and rigor. Under such a system, our prized idiosyncrasies and powerful identities would remain intact. The programs and services that support the scholarly enterprise would become a true system.

CLIR will seek partners to develop methods, guidelines, and recommendations that will help academic leaders instantiate sustainable communities of practice to produce a new, more logical and rational system of higher education. CLIR will guide and coordinate efforts to promote standardization and more rapid systemic adoption of tools and applications. This work may involve the creation of new communities—virtual organizations that transcend geographic and institutional boundaries and that share interlocking technical and social elements.

In this respect, the reintegration of the Digital Library Federation (DLF) as a program within CLIR is timely. As CLIR works to explore and develop simulations for various macro solutions, DLF will provide the network of technical expertise and managerial acumen by which many of these large-scale applications can be engineered. DLF, as part of its mandate, continues to focus on the technological aspects of developing, sustaining, and federating digital libraries; promoting standards, protocols, and best practices; evaluating and promulgating digital library projects and programs; and supporting digital architectures that most effectively allow for interoperable and extensible digital resources and tools. The DLF Forum remains an important venue for better understanding the elements and complexity of digital library evolution, and for assessing and sharing research and development relevant to digital libraries. In this respect, the newly invigorated Federation and its Forum are ideal means to broker, test, and ultimately instantiate macro solutions.

There is no question that we are at a turning point. As with so many aspects of the digital revolution, our future will hinge less on technological innovation than on informed and empathetic leadership. A new kind of leadership is needed. CLIR is uniquely positioned to help define and promote lasting solutions that are efficient, effective, and elegant.

Charles Henry
November 2010

THE PROGRAMS

July 1, 2009–June 30, 2010

CYBERINFRASTRUCTURE

Digital Library Federation Program

On July 1, 2009, the Digital Library Federation ceased independent operation and merged with CLIR to become the Digital Library Federation Program. A transition committee was formed to review and make recommendations about the future direction of the program; address issues pertaining to sponsorship criteria, benefits, fees, and promulgation of mission; articulate the qualities and skills requisite for the next program director, and plan for the Fall 2009 Forum. In May 2010, CLIR appointed Rachel Frick director of the Digital Library Federation Program. At the same time, CLIR established the Digital Library Program Advisory Committee (see p. 16).

DLF Transition Advisory Committee

Fred Heath, University of Texas at Austin
Geneva Henry, Center for Digital Scholarship,
 Rice University
Paula Kaufman, University of Illinois,
 Urbana-Champaign
Rick Luce, Emory University
James Neal, Columbia University
Winston Tabb, Johns Hopkins University

The Fall 2009 Forum, held November 11–12 in Long Beach, California, focused on innovation in library technology and gave participants a chance to share their views about the potential role of the new DLF Program. Forum attendees suggested that core DLF Program activities should include sharing best practices, sponsoring training and in-depth discussions, offering individual and institutional mentoring, serving as a bridge between administrators and developers, and fostering partnerships.

Assessment of Digging into Data Challenge

In January 2010, CLIR entered a cooperative agreement with the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) Office of Digital Humanities to provide a strategic assessment of the Digging into Data (DID) Challenge, a grant competition jointly sponsored by NEH, the U.K.'s Joint Information Systems Committee (JISC), the U.S. National Science Foundation (NSF), and Canada's Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (SSHRC). The goals of the DID Challenge are to encourage multidisciplinary collaborations that explore the application of computational techniques to large corpora and to begin to understand the kinds of research that become possible when advanced search algorithms are applied to these corpora. The program's sponsors announced the first eight awards in December 2009.

The CLIR-NEH cooperative assessment will address how well the DID Challenge met its objectives and identify the next steps agencies and researchers might take to best support continued development in this area. The project team is organizing focus group meetings, interviews, and site visits with grantees, program officers, and experts to inform the assessment.

Following the conclusion of the DID Challenge funding cycle in June 2011, CLIR will issue two final reports. The first report will be a technical summary that addresses the assessment's goals, administrative history, methodology, summary of findings, next steps, and recommendations. The second will discuss implications of the findings for the future of computationally intensive scholarship in the humanities, and for the roles of public and private funding agencies in fostering this research.

Infrastructure for Humanities Scholarship

In October 2009, CLIR and Tufts University initiated a collaborative planning process to identify what is needed to advance an infrastructure to support humanities scholarship, with particular focus on the classics. The project, funded by the Institute for Museum and Library Services, engages scholars and academic librarians in examining the services and digital objects classicists have developed, the future needs of the discipline, and the roles of libraries and other curatorial institutions in fostering the infrastructure on which the core intellectual activities of classics and many other disciplines depend. On the basis of consultation with librarians, archivists, and humanities scholars, project staff aim to identify and describe a set of shared services layered over a distributed storage architecture that is seamless to end users, allows multiple contributors, and leverages institutional resources and facilities. Much of this architecture exists at the individual project and institutional levels; the challenge is to identify the suite of shared services to be developed.

A steering committee composed of librarians, subject bibliographers, archivists, research scholars, and library-based computer scientists was organized in November 2009, and coprincipal investigators Gregory Crane and Amy Friedlander consulted with scholars and other stakeholders through the winter and spring of 2010. Meanwhile, Alison Jones, of Tufts University, undertook a review of digital projects in the classics to identify existing services, resources, and needs. A meeting is scheduled for fall 2010 to discuss the review and outline a plan for future work.

A Distant Symmetry

With support from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, CLIR commissioned a study to investigate the possible relevance of declassified tools developed by the intelligence community to humanistic scholarship. The

intelligence community faces many of the same challenges as digital humanists do, including processing vast corpora of texts and translating and working in multiple languages. This inquiry sought to determine what, if anything, the digital humanities community can learn from the digital research tools developed by the intelligence community. Amelia Acker and Katie Shilton, both Ph.D. students in the Department of Information Studies at the University of California, Los Angeles, conducted the study. Their research focused on two questions: (1) What tools exist in the intelligence communities, and are these tools accessible to humanities scholars? and (2) If a scholar can find a link to the tool, is there sufficient information for the investigator to understand its requirements as well as the relevance of the tool to the proposed research? Acker and Shilton's findings are presented in "A Distant Symmetry, Final Report: U.S. Intelligence Community Tools," available at <http://www.clir.org/pubs/archives/Acker-Shilton2010.pdf>.

THE NEXT SCHOLAR

Postdoctoral Fellowship in Academic Libraries

The Postdoctoral Fellowship in Academic Libraries Program, now in its seventh year, provides recent Ph.D. recipients an opportunity to develop expertise in new forms of scholarly research and the information resources that support them, both traditional and digital. CLIR postdoctoral fellows work on projects that forge, renovate, and strengthen connections between academic library collections and their users. Fellows have consulted on integrating library materials and resources into the classroom, designed and implemented metadata standards, curated exhibitions in libraries and museums, organized conferences and colloquia, taught courses, written successful grant proposals for host institutions, managed archives, created Web portals, and more. Participating libraries benefit from the expertise of accomplished humanists, social scientists, and scientists who invigorate approaches to collection use and teaching, contribute field-specific knowledge, and provide insight into the future of scholarship. To date, 45 fellows have participated in the program.

2010–2011 Postdoctoral Fellows in Academic Libraries

<i>New Fellows</i>	<i>Host Institution</i>
Andrew Asher	Bucknell University
Tamar Boyadjian	University of California, Los Angeles
Brian Croxall	Emory University
John Maclachlan	McMaster University
Julia Osman	Arizona State Library, Archives and Public Records
Yi Shen	Johns Hopkins University
Mike Snowdon	McMaster University
<i>Continuing Fellows</i>	<i>Host Institution</i>
Anne Bruder	Bryn Mawr College
Daniel Chamberlain	Occidental College
Timothy F. Jackson	University of Nebraska-Lincoln
Lori Jahnke	The College of Physicians of Philadelphia
Noah Shenker	McMaster University

Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives: Building a New Research Environment

Launched in 2008 with the support of The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, CLIR's Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives Program supports heritage organizations engaged in describing valuable cultural materials that are unknown or underutilized. In 2009, CLIR issued the program's second call for proposals. A review panel selected 14 projects, to which a total of \$4 million was awarded.

The 29 projects funded to date represent a wide range of institutions from across the United States and involve collections of books, other printed matter, manuscripts, personal papers, photography, audio and video recordings, specimens, artworks, artifacts, maps, posters, ephemera, architectural materials, and more.

To gain a better understanding of the concerns of the librarians and archivists tasked with describing hidden collections, CLIR began work with a team of researchers to develop an outreach program framed as a study titled “Observations on Scholarly Engagement with Hidden Special Collections and Archives.” The team includes eight former participants in CLIR’s Postdoctoral Fellowship in Academic Libraries Program. The aim of the study is to describe successful strategies for engaging expert users with collections. The team has collected data from 2008 and 2009 grant recipients through an anonymous survey and a series of on-site interviews with project staff. In spring 2010, the team summarized findings in an interim report that is available at <http://www.clir.org/hiddencollections/engagement/engagement.html/>.

2009-2010 Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives Awards

Brooklyn Historical Society: Uncovering the Secrets of Brooklyn’s 19th-Century Past: Creation to Consolidation, \$440,491

The California Digital Library: Uncovering California’s Environmental Collections: A Collaborative Approach, \$446,817

College of Charleston Libraries: Jewish Heritage Collection, \$184,000

Free Library of Philadelphia: Milestones in 20th-Century American Children’s Literature at the Free Library of Philadelphia, \$264,945

George Mason University: Uncovering a Forbidden World: Providing Access to East German Art, Culture, and Politics, \$76,800

Lehigh University: The Moravian Community in the New World: The First 100 Years, \$90,552

Marquette University Libraries: Catholic Social Action Access Project, \$149,964

Newberry Library: French Pamphlet Collections at the Newberry Library, \$488,179

North Carolina State University Libraries: Changing the Landscape: Exposing the Legacy of Modernist Architects and Landscape Architects, \$221,023

Northeast Historic Film: Intellectual Access to Moving Images of Work Life, 1916–1950, \$214,626

Smithsonian Institution: Exposing Biodiversity Fieldbooks and Original Expedition Journals at the Smithsonian Institution, \$498,239

University of California, Berkeley: *San Francisco Examiner* Photograph Archive Project, \$306,446

University of Southern California Libraries: Excavating L.A.: USC’s Hidden Southern California Historical Collections, \$160,000

Yale University: Song, Speech, and Dance: Special Collections from the Recorded-Sound Archives at Yale and Stanford Universities, \$457,776

More detail on this year’s funded projects can be found at <http://www.clir.org/hiddencollections/awards/index2009.html>.

Also in the spring, CLIR sponsored a symposium for grant recipients in Washington, D.C. Seventy-two participants attended the two-day meeting. The agenda, presentation slides, and digital copies of posters contributed by participants are available at <http://www.clir.org/hiddencollections/symposium20100329.html>.

CLIR issued the program's third call for proposals in March 2010. The next round of grant recipients will be announced in December.

2010–2011 Mellon Dissertation Fellows

Faiz Ahmed, University of California, Berkeley
Norah Andrews, Johns Hopkins University
Megan Barber, University of California, Santa Barbara
Juandrea Bates, University of Texas at Austin
Jacob Baum, University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign
Roland Clark, University of Pittsburgh
Christine DeLucia, Yale University
Amy Dunagin, Yale University
Rohit Goel, University of Chicago
Benjamin Graham, University of Michigan
Philipp Lehmann, Harvard University
Pablo Palomino, University of California, Berkeley
Kelly Summers, Stanford University
Samuel Thrope, University of California, Berkeley

Mellon Dissertation Fellowships

In 2010, 14 graduate students were selected to receive Mellon Dissertation Fellowships. The fellowship program, now entering its tenth year, is intended to help graduate students in the humanities and related social science fields pursue doctoral research using original sources and gain skill and creativity in using primary source materials in libraries, archives, museums, and related repositories. Each fellowship carries a maximum stipend of \$25,000 and supports dissertation research for up to 12 months. To date, the program has supported 111 graduate students who have carried out their dissertation research in public and private libraries and archives worldwide.

PRESERVATION

Preserving Recorded Sound Heritage

CLIR continues to work with the Library of Congress's National Recording Preservation Board on a congressionally mandated study of the state of audio preservation in the United States. The study comprises a series of reports examining the issues that threaten the long-term survival of our recorded sound heritage. In September 2009, CLIR and the Library of Congress published *Protection for Pre-1972 Sound Recordings under State Law and Its Impact on Use by Nonprofit Institutions: A 10-State Analysis*, prepared by the Program on Information Justice and Intellectual Property, Washington College of Law, American University, under the supervision of Peter Jaszi with the assistance of Nick Lewis. The study examines criminal and civil laws of 10 states, as well as judicial decisions and common law, pertaining to sound recordings fixed before 1972. The authors provide a brief history of the formulation of these laws and examine the laws and court cases that may determine the extent to which nonprofit institutions may preserve and disseminate pre-1972 recordings.

Throughout the first half of 2010, CLIR staff worked in an editorial partnership with Sam Brylawski and Rob Bamberger, authors of *The State of Recorded Sound Preservation in the United States: A National Legacy at Risk in the Digital Age*. The report, copublished by CLIR and the Library of Congress in August 2010, is the culmination of nearly 10 years of investigation

and commissioned research on technical, legal, and educational dimensions of the challenges facing recorded sound preservation. The report lays the groundwork for a National Recording Preservation Plan, which the Library will present to Congress in late 2010 or 2011.

Blue Ribbon Task Force on Economically Sustainable Digital Preservation

In February 2010, the Blue Ribbon Task Force on Economically Sustainable Digital Preservation and Access issued its final report, *Sustainable Economics for a Digital Planet: Ensuring Long-Term Access to Digital Information*.

CLIR was an institutional participant in the task force since its formation in 2007. Funded by the National Science Foundation and The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the task force was created to identify sustainable economic models for providing access to the ever-growing amount of digital information in the public interest.

NEW MODELS

The Idea of Order

In June 2010, CLIR published *The Idea of Order: Transforming Research Collections for 21st-Century Scholarship*, which explores the transition from an analog to a digital environment for knowledge access, preservation, and reconstitution, and the implications of this transition for managing research collections. The volume comprises three reports. The first, “Can a New Research Library Be All-Digital?” by Lisa Spiro and Geneva Henry, explores the degree to which a new research library can eschew print. The second, “On the Cost of Keeping a Book,” by Paul Courant and Matthew “Buzzy” Nielsen, argues that from the perspective of long-term storage, digital surrogates offer a considerable cost savings over print-based libraries. The final report, “Ghostlier Demarcations,” examines how well large text databases being created by Google Books and other mass-digitization efforts meet the needs of scholars, and the larger implications of these projects for research, teaching, and publishing.

CLIR President Charles Henry introduces the volume by suggesting that the digital environment may be fundamentally changing how the mind acquires and retains knowledge. In a concluding chapter, Roger Schonfeld of ITHAKA S&R observes the tension that research libraries face between fulfilling their time-honored role as custodians of scholarship and enabling a digital environment for scholars, and notes the growing potential for systemwide responses to mitigate this tension.

Toward a Cloud Library

With support from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, CLIR initiated a research project entitled “Toward a Cloud Library.” This project evaluated

combining large-scale virtual and print repositories as surrogates for library collections, using the New York University libraries as a case study. The goal was to identify the policies, procedures, logistics, and infrastructure that print and digital repositories need to make their services more widely available to university libraries, and to enable libraries to make more effective use of these repositories in managing their own collections. In this research project, CLIR also worked with the Columbia University Libraries and their off-site book-depository program (ReCAP), the HathiTrust, and OCLC.

Feasibility of an Open-Access NSF Publication Repository

In October 2009, CLIR partnered with the Johns Hopkins University and the University of Michigan on a study to examine the feasibility of developing, operating, and sustaining an open-access repository (or set of repositories) of articles from National Science Foundation (NSF)-sponsored research. To secure community input into the study, in January 2010, CLIR hosted three workshops on the policy, technical, and business/organization requirements for sustaining such a repository. The study, to be completed early in 2011, will evaluate several approaches to establishing a repository, delineate the advantages and disadvantages of each approach, and present a recommendation to NSF.

THE EMERGING LIBRARY

Workshops on Faculty Research Behavior and on Undergraduate Work Practices

In 2007, CLIR began offering faculty research behavior workshops, which teach information professionals ethnographic techniques that enable them to understand faculty members' work practices and how library and information services can address real faculty needs. Teams of librarians and instructional technologists from 57 colleges and universities have attended the workshops; sites have included Wesleyan University, Kenyon College, Cornell University, the University of California at Berkeley, George Washington University, the University of Rochester, New York University, the University of Miami, the University of New Mexico, and the University of Washington. The workshops are led by Nancy Foster, director of anthropological research at the River Campus Libraries at the University of Rochester.

Building on the success of the faculty workshops, CLIR initiated a series of undergraduate work practices workshops, also led by Foster. The first of these sessions was held at New York University in November 2009; the second took place at the University of South Florida in January 2010. At these sessions, teams from CLIR's sponsoring institutions learn techniques for understanding how undergraduates do their work, especially how

CLIR Chief Information Officers Group Members (as of 6/30/10)

Christopher Barth, Luther College
Param Bedi, Bucknell University
Theresa Byrd, Ohio Wesleyan University
Jim Cubit, Lake Forest College
Jose Dieudonne, Arcadia University
Greg Diment, Kalamazoo College
Charling Chang Fagan, Sarah Lawrence College
Carol Falcione, Barnard College
Chris Ferguson, Pacific Lutheran University
Megan Fitch, Beloit College
Chip German, Millersville College
Ronald Griggs, Kenyon College
Perry Hanson, Brandeis University
Lee Hisle, Connecticut College
Rick Holmgren, Allegheny College
Robert Johnson, Rhodes College
Kenneth Kochien, Colby-Sawyer College
Renee Jadushlever, Mills College
Felice Maciejewski, Saint Norbert College
Neil McElroy, Lafayette College
Pam McQuesten, Occidental College
Kathy Monday, University of Richmond
Pattie Orr, Baylor University
Charlotte Slocum Patriquin, Mount Holyoke College
Rick Provine, DePauw University
Robert Renaud, Dickinson College
Suzanne Risley, Mitchell College
Mike Roy, Middlebury College
Vicki Sells, Sewanee: The University of the South
Elliott Shore, Bryn Mawr College
Scott Silverman, Earlham College
Carol Smith, DePauw University
Bruce Taggart, Lehigh University
Gene Wiemers, Bates College
Frank Wojcik, The College at Brockport, State
 University of New York

they use library resources, staff, and facilities in writing research papers and completing research-based assignments. Following the workshops, participants share ideas, current research and publications, and suggestions through a listserv.

CLIR will continue sponsoring both types of workshops in 2011.

CLIR Chief Information Officers Group

CLIR's Chief Information Officers (CIO) Group is composed of 35 directors of organizations that have merged their library and technology units on liberal arts college campuses. The group met in November 2009 and May 2010 to discuss organizational and policy issues that are unique to their environments. They explored such topics as open access; how the recession has affected organizational structure, technology, business strategies, and attitudes; cloud computing; portals versus Web 2.0; measuring the use and effectiveness of services; and ideas for prioritizing services. Throughout the year members exchange ideas and solutions through a listserv.

LEADERSHIP

Leadership through New Communities of Knowledge

Leadership through New Communities of Knowledge, a partnership between CLIR and the Council of Independent Colleges (CIC), offers professional development opportunities for library staff at small-to-midsize private colleges and universities. Launched in July 2009, the project is supported with funds from the Institute of Museum and Library Services.

In fall 2009, CLIR Program Associate Lori Miller worked with David Consiglio of the Merged Information Services Organization (MISO) at Bryn Mawr College to construct and administer a survey to gauge the interest of CIC institutions in diverse workshop topics, some of which CLIR had offered in the past. Of the topics queried, managing digital assets and work restructuring garnered the most interest, while student research behavior emerged as a popular idea for a workshop not originally slated for the project.

To address the interest in managing digital assets, CLIR negotiated a partnership with the University of North Carolina (UNC) at Chapel Hill to send 12 participants from CIC schools to UNC's 2010 DigCCurr Professional Institute on "Curation Practices for the Digital Object Lifecycle." The group spent a week in May 2010 in Chapel Hill under the leadership of key practitioners such as Seamus Ross, Helen Tibbo, and Manfred Thaller. Participants benefited from sessions on issues such as digital preservation and managing in response to technological change; they also

engaged in hands-on sessions with software such as DRAMBORA. To address the interest in work restructuring, CLIR contracted with Maureen Sullivan, of Maureen Sullivan Associates, to conduct a workshop titled “Work Restructuring in the Library,” which took place in July 2010.

In March 2010, CIC held the first in its series of “Information Fluency in the Disciplines” workshops, which focused on the discipline of literature and drew teams from 23 CIC institutions.

Frye Leadership Institute

In 2010, the Frye Institute took a one-year hiatus to develop and articulate a new program that addresses higher education’s leadership needs in an era of unprecedented change. The next Frye Leadership Institute, to be jointly sponsored by CLIR, EDUCAUSE, and Emory University, will be held in Atlanta, Georgia, June 5–10, 2011.

In its new iteration, Frye will engage those who are already leaders in their profession and further develop their skills, particularly in the area of advocacy. The institute will address challenges in higher education through a variety of topics, empowering librarians and information technologists to start conversations and take action on issues that are important not only to their own institutions but also to the entire higher education community. The Frye Leadership Institute seeks to foster leaders, particularly in the information sector, who can inspire, advocate, and implement fundamental collaborative change.

Zipf Fellowship

Lynn Yarmey, a master’s-degree student in the Graduate School of Library and Information Science at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, was selected to receive the A. R. Zipf Fellowship in Information Management for 2010. Her research focuses on the role of controlled vocabularies in translating knowledge into machine-readable form and increasing local retrieval through improved information capture and discovery.

The Zipf Fellowship is awarded annually to the graduate student in a field of information management or systems who best exemplifies the ideals of Al Zipf, the information science pioneer for whom the award is named.

INTERNATIONAL

Global Digital Libraries Collaborative

In November 2009, CLIR and Stanford University organized a meeting to identify opportunities for international collaboration in digital library research and development. Sixty-one library administrators and senior technologists, representing 13 countries and 24 institutions, met

at Stanford University for three days to discuss the challenges and opportunities afforded by the prospect of developing truly integrated global digital libraries.

While the concerns of the group were varied, participants were enthusiastic about extending their collections and services through unprecedented integration of their digital collections with those of others. Participants identified a list of promising initiatives that are worthy of support by the international library community. This list is available on CLIR's Web site and is included in a report of the meeting issued in January 2010. The British Library hosted a second meeting for this group in May 2010, devoted to the topic of linked data. That meeting's discussions resulted in the identification of four priority areas for development related to the implementation of linked data in libraries.

Rovelstad Scholarship in International Librarianship

Instituted in 2002, the Rovelstad Scholarship encourages library students who have an interest in international library work by enabling them to attend the World Library and Information Congress, the annual meeting of the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions. Amy Neeser, who is pursuing her MLIS degree at the University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee's School of Information Studies, received this year's award. She has a bachelor's degree in German studies from the University of Minnesota, and for the past three years has been working as the language services, publicity, and technology coordinator at the nonprofit Germanic-American Institute in St. Paul, Minnesota.

ADVISORY GROUPS

AS OF JUNE 30, 2010

Academic Librarians Advisory Committee

Tyrone Cannon
University of San Francisco

Sam Demas
Carleton College

Charles Henry
Council on Library and Information
Resources

Lynn Scott Cochrane
Denison University

Connie Vinita Dowell
San Diego State University

Joanne Schneider
Colgate University

A. R. Zipf Fellowship Selection Committee

Christine Borgman
University of California, Los Angeles

Deanna B. Marcum
Library of Congress

Rena Zipf

Digital Library Federation Program Advisory Committee

Eric Celeste
Minneapolis, MN

Katherine Kott
Stanford University

Diana Oblinger
EDUCAUSE

Sayed Choudhury
Johns Hopkins University

Clifford Lynch
Coalition for Networked Information

Elliott Shore
Bryn Mawr College

Geneva Henry
Rice University

James Neal
Columbia University

John Wilkin
HathiTrust

Joseph King
National Institute for Technology in Liberal
Education

Hidden Collections Review Panel

Amy Friedlander
Council on Library and Information
Resources

Geneva Henry
Rice University

Jerome McGann
University of Virginia

Joan Giesecke
University of Nebraska at Lincoln

Michael Keller
Stanford University

Stephen G. Nichols
Johns Hopkins University

Jacqueline Goldsby
University of Chicago

Mary Kelley
University of Michigan

Elliott Shore
Bryn Mawr College

Charles Henry
Council on Library and Information
Resources

Ronald L. Larsen
University of Pittsburgh

Richard V. Szary
University of North Carolina at
Chapel Hill

Mellon Fellowships Selection Committee 2010

Frederick Colby
University of Oregon

Nancy Foster
University of Rochester

Meg Norcia
State University of New York, Brockport

Mark Dimunation
Library of Congress

Charles Henry
Council on Library and Information
Resources

Alisha Rankin
Tufts University

Stephen Enniss
Folger Shakespeare Library

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS

ACTIVE IN THE PERIOD JULY 1, 2009 TO JUNE 30, 2010

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Amelia Acker Los Angeles, CA	To conduct a literature review to discover declassified computational tools created by the intelligence agencies that may be of use to humanists	7/13/2009	\$5,000
Amelia Acker and Katherine Shilton Los Angeles, CA	To evaluate 41 Web-accessible computational tools created by the intelligence agencies that may be of use to humanists	1/4/2009	\$10,000
Amistad Research Center New Orleans, LA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Working for Freedom: Documenting Civil Rights Organization"	1/23/2009	\$250,000
Avery Research Center for African American History Charleston, SC	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Providing Access to African American Collections at the Avery Research Center"	12/1/2008	\$236,920
Paul Ayris London, UK	To support broader participation in the Open Access Workshops in CERN in Geneva in June 2009	5/1/2009	\$10,000
The British Library London, UK	To support an intern to work on the economic validation and cost modeling of the preservation components of the life cycle work	11/22/2008	\$10,000
Brooklyn Historical Society Brooklyn, NY	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Uncovering the Secrets of Brooklyn's 19th Century Past: Creation to Consolidation"	11/13/2009	\$440,491
Marta Brunner Los Angeles, CA	To serve as coordinator of CLIR's monthly Postdoctoral Fellows Synchronous Sessions	10/7/2009	\$2,400
California Digital Library Oakland, CA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Uncovering California's Environmental Collections: A Collaborative Approach"	11/13/2009	\$446,817
California Historical Society San Francisco, CA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "California Ephemera Project"	12/1/2008	\$247,738
Eric Celeste St. Paul, MN	To serve as a senior advisor to CLIR, focusing on the DLF transition period	8/6/2009	\$46,000
Eric Celeste St. Paul, MN	To retain services as part-time Web developer for trouble shooting and technical support of the DLF Web site	7/15/2009	\$3,000
Center for the History of Medicine Boston, MA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Foundations of Public Health Policy"	12/1/2008	\$217,933
College of Charleston Charleston, SC	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the cataloging of the library's Jewish Heritage Collection	11/13/2009	\$184,000

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
David Consiglio Bryn Mawr, PA	To develop and administer two surveys in support of the "Leadership through New Communities of Knowledge" program	9/25/2009	\$5,000
Cornell University Ithaca, NY	To conduct a joint user needs study of graduate students in the humanities at Cornell and Columbia Universities	1/18/2010	\$15,000
Paul Courant Ann Arbor, MI	To conduct a study on the cost of accessing and storing printed volumes in academic libraries	6/19/2008	\$4,000
Lori Eakin Hillsborough, NC	To support the Blue Ribbon Task Force on Economic Sustainability	1/22/2008	\$44,000
Emory University Atlanta, GA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Archives from Atlanta, Cradle of the Civil Rights Movement: the papers of Andrew Young, SCLC, and NAACP-Atlanta, GA"	1/23/2009	\$399,172
Kathleen Fear Ann Arbor, MI	To serve as rapporteur for three meetings on feasibility of open access repository for NSF sponsored research	1/22/10	\$1,500
Free Library of Philadelphia Philadelphia, PA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Milestones in 20th Century American Children's Literature at the Free Library of Philadelphia"	11/13/2009	\$264,945
George Mason University Fairfax, VA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Uncovering a Forbidden World: Providing Access to East German Art, Culture, and Politics"	11/13/2009	\$76,800
George Mason University Fairfax, VA	To support librarian participation in THATCamp 2010-2011 unconferences	6/11/2010	\$5,000
Getty Research Institute Los Angeles, CA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Uncovering Archives and Rare Photographs: Two Models for Creating Accession-level Finding Aids Using Archivists' Toolkit"	12/1/2008	\$274,889
Goucher College Baltimore, MD	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Mapping Special Collections for Research and Teaching at Goucher College"	12/1/2008	\$198,121
Intelligent Television New York, NY	To organize panels of professionals from the fields of media, education, and technology for the public opening of the Library of Congress's Culpeper campus	7/8/08	\$45,000
Todd Krater Lakemoor, IL	To process applications for long-term storage for a variety of CLIR's programs	9/3/2009	\$3,000
Jon Kertzer Seattle, WA	To research and explore nonprofit fundraising opportunities for archives and others in the field of recorded sound	1/11/2010	\$59,000

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Lehigh University Bethlehem, PA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "The Moravian Community in the New World: The First 100 Years"	11/13/2009	\$90,552
Library of Congress Washington, DC	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Library of Congress Multi-Sheet Map Series Collection: Africa"	12/1/2008	\$240,240
Litchfield Historical Society Litchfield, CT	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Revolutionary Era and Early Republic Holdings"	12/1/2008	\$101,209
Marquette University Milwaukee, WI	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Catholic Social Action Access Project"	11/13/2009	\$149,964
Shawn Martin Philadelphia, PA	To convene a meeting on the topic of sustainable open access business models for libraries	11/26/2008	\$5,000
Kelly Miller Charlottesville, VA	To organize and manage the project "Best Practices for Scholarly Engagement with Hidden Special Collections and Archives"	12/1/2008	\$63,500
Newberry Library Chicago, IL	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "French Pamphlet Collections at the Newberry Library"	11/13/2009	\$488,179
New York University New York, NY	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Records of the Communist Party, USA and Library of Reference Center for Marxist Studies"	12/1/2008	\$492,901
North Carolina State University Libraries Raleigh, NC	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Changing the Landscape: Exposing the Legacy of Modernist Architects and Landscape Architects"	11/13/2009	\$221,023
Northeast Historic Film Bucksport, ME	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Intellectual Access to Moving Images of Work Life, 1916-1950"	11/13/2009	\$214,626
Northwestern University Library Evanston, IL	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Africana Posters: a collaboration with Northwestern University and Michigan State University"	12/1/2008	\$89,733
Tufts University Medford, MA	To perform the services set forth in proposal narrative to IMLS "Collaborative Planning for an Infrastructure to support Humanities Scholarship"	11/3/2009	\$25,000
Regents of the University of California Berkeley, CA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "San Francisco Examiner Photograph Archive Project"	11/13/2009	\$306,446
Rice University Houston, TX	To explore the feasibility of establishing a primarily digital library to support the teaching and research needs of a university	12/11/2008	\$9,438
Robert W. Woodruff Library Atlanta, GA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Processing Voter Education Project Collection"	1/23/2009	\$249,461

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
University of Brighton Brighton, UK	To continue to serve as information director for the <i>Association for Computing Machinery Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage</i>	12/23/2009	\$10,000
Smithsonian Institution Washington, DC	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Exposing Biodiversity Fieldbooks and Original Expedition Journals at the Smithsonian Institution"	11/13/2009	\$498,239
Maureen Sullivan Annapolis, MD	To develop a workshop in support of the IMLS/CLIR project "Leadership Through New Communities of Knowledge"	3/25/2010	\$5,800
University of California, Berkeley Berkeley, CA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "University and Jepson Herbaria"	12/1/2008	\$253,794
University of California, Los Angeles Los Angeles, CA	To support the UCLA Library's undergraduate capstone seminars program	11/7/2008	\$10,000
University of Michigan Ann Arbor, MI	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Collaboration in Cataloging: Islamic Manuscripts at Michigan"	12/1/2008	\$225,931
University of Pennsylvania Philadelphia, PA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Hidden Collections in the Philadelphia Area: A Consortial Processing and Cataloging Initiative"	12/16/2008	\$500,000
University of Rochester Rochester, NY	To support four faculty research/undergraduate research behavior workshops led by Nancy Fried Foster	11/30/2009	\$12,000
University of Rochester Rochester, NY	To support three workshops on faculty research behavior, led by Nancy Fried Foster	12/4/2008	\$9,000
University of Southern California Libraries Los Angeles, CA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Excavating L.A.: USC's Hidden Southern California Historical Collections"	11/13/2009	\$160,000
Yale University New Haven, CT	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Song, Speech, and Dance: Special Collections from the Recorded Sound Archives at Yale and Stanford Universities"	11/13/2009	\$457,776

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

**FINANCIAL STATEMENTS
WITH
ADDITIONAL INFORMATION**

**FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 2010
WITH
INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT**

**STONE AND SPRING
Certified Public Accountants
Herndon, Virginia**

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

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Michael G. Spring, Jr., C.P.A.
Stephen C. Stone, C.P.A.

INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT

To the Board of Directors
Council on Library and Information Resources
Washington, DC

We have audited the accompanying statement of financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources (a nonprofit organization) as of June 30, 2010, and the related statement of activities and changes in net assets, and cash flows for the year then ended. These financial statements are the responsibility of the Council on Library and Information Resources' management. Our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audit.

We conducted our audit in accordance with auditing standards generally accepted in the United States of America. Those standards require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free of material misstatement. An audit includes examining, on a test basis, evidence supporting the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements. An audit also includes assessing the accounting principles used and significant estimates made by management, as well as evaluating the overall financial statement presentation. We believe that our audit provides a reasonable basis for our opinion.

In our opinion, the financial statements referred to above present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources as of June 30, 2010, and the changes in its net assets and its cash flows for the year then ended in conformity with accounting principles generally accepted in the United States of America.

Our audit was conducted for the purpose of forming an opinion on the basic financial statements taken as a whole. The schedule of functional expenses on page 33 and 34 is presented for purposes of additional analysis and is not a required part of the basic financial statements. Such information has been subjected to the auditing procedures applied in the audit of the basic financial statements and, in our opinion, is fairly stated in all material respects in relation to the basic financial statements taken as a whole.

Certified Public Accountants

Herndon, Virginia
October 17, 2010

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION

June 30, 2010

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Temporarily Restricted</u>	<u>Total 2010</u>
Assets			
Cash and cash equivalents	\$ 948,078	\$ 761,695	\$ 1,709,773
Investments	-	778,699	778,699
Accounts receivable	96,328	600,000	696,328
Furniture and equipment, net	38,290	-	38,290
Other assets	<u>123,637</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>123,637</u>
Total Assets	<u>\$ 1,206,333</u>	<u>\$ 2,140,394</u>	<u>\$ 3,346,727</u>
Liabilities and Net Assets			
Accounts payable	\$ 63,758	\$ -	\$ 63,758
Capital Lease	8,910	-	8,910
Accrued expenses	<u>73,447</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>73,447</u>
Total Liabilities	<u>\$ 146,115</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 146,115</u>
Net Assets	<u>\$ 1,060,218</u>	<u>\$ 2,140,394</u>	<u>\$ 3,200,612</u>
Total Liabilities and Net Assets	<u>\$ 1,206,333</u>	<u>\$ 2,140,394</u>	<u>\$ 3,346,727</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements
are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF ACTIVITIES AND CHANGES IN NET ASSETS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2010

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Temporarily Restricted</u>	<u>Total 2010</u>
Revenue			
Grants and contracts	\$ 439,047	\$ 1,737,000	\$ 2,176,047
Contributions	607,990	-	607,990
Publication sales	2,532	-	2,532
Investment income/(loss)	22,450	129,784	152,234
Other income	<u>44,679</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>44,679</u>
	<u>\$ 1,116,698</u>	<u>\$ 1,866,784</u>	<u>\$ 2,983,482</u>
Net Assets released from restrictions			
Satisfaction of program restrictions	<u>\$ 5,838,291</u>	<u>\$ (5,838,291)</u>	<u>\$ -</u>
Total Revenue	<u>\$ 6,954,989</u>	<u>\$ (3,971,507)</u>	<u>\$ 2,983,482</u>
Expenses			
Program services:			
Preservation	\$ 532,808	\$ -	\$ 532,808
Digital Library	261,983	-	261,983
Leadership	107,270	-	107,270
Other	128,897	-	128,897
Cyberinfrastructure	227,342	-	227,342
International Developments	93,429	-	93,429
The next scholar	<u>5,010,388</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>5,010,388</u>
Total Program services	\$ 6,362,117	\$ -	\$ 6,362,117
Administration	<u>943,569</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>943,569</u>
Total Expenses	<u>\$ 7,305,686</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 7,305,686</u>
Transfer from Digital Library Federation	\$ 516,398	\$ -	\$ 516,398
Change in Net Assets	\$ (350,697)	\$ (3,971,507)	\$ (4,322,204)
Net Assets, Beginning of Year	<u>\$ 894,517</u>	<u>\$ 6,111,901</u>	<u>\$ 7,006,418</u>
Net Assets, End of Year	<u>\$ 1,060,218</u>	<u>\$ 2,140,394</u>	<u>\$ 3,200,612</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF CASH FLOWS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2010

Operating Activities	
Change in net assets	\$ (4,322,204)
Adjustments to reconcile change in net assets to net cash provided by (used) in operating activities	
Depreciation	16,475
Transfer from Digital Library Federation	516,398
Unrealized (gain) loss on investments	(69,787)
Realized (gain) loss on investments	(36,176)
(Increase) decrease in other assets	(24,046)
(Increase) decrease in accounts receivable	3,352,733
Increase (decrease) in accounts payable and accrued expenses	<u>(606,648)</u>
Net Cash Provided (used) By Operating Activities	\$ <u>(1,173,255)</u>
Investing Activities	
Proceeds from sales of investments	\$ 2,258,600
Purchases of investments	(1,277,082)
Purchases of furniture and equipment	<u>(17,117)</u>
Net Cash Provided (used) By Investing Activities	\$ <u>964,401</u>
Financing Activities	
Proceeds from capital lease	\$ 9,720
Principal payments on capital lease	<u>(810)</u>
Net Cash Provided (used) By Financing Activities	\$ <u>8,910</u>
Net Change in Cash and Cash Equivalents	\$ (199,944)
Cash and cash equivalents, beginning of year	<u>1,909,717</u>
Cash and cash equivalents, end of year	\$ <u>1,709,773</u>
Supplemental Cash Flow Information	
Interest paid during the year	\$ _____

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2010

NOTE 1- Organization

The Council on Library and Information Resources is a not-for-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1988 for the purpose of fostering, developing, and supporting systematic and purposeful collaboration in order to ensure the preservation of the published and documentary record in all formats and provide equitable access to that information.

The Council on Library and Information Resources operations are financed through contributions from colleges, universities and other organizations and through general support grants and restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council on Library and Information Resources conducts its work directly through committees and working groups as well as through contracts with other organizations and individuals.

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

Basis of accounting - The accompanying financial statements of the Council on Library and Information Resources have been prepared on the accrual basis.

Grant revenue and recognition of grantor restrictions - The Council on Library and Information Resources reports grants as temporarily restricted support if they are received with grantor stipulations that limit the use of the grants as to time or purpose. When either condition is satisfied, temporarily restricted net assets are reclassified to unrestricted net assets and reported in the statement of activities and changes in net assets as net assets released from restrictions. Support that is restricted by the grantor is reported as an increase in unrestricted net assets if the restriction expires in the reporting period in which the support is recognized.

Contracts / Grants payable - Contracts made by the Council on Library and Information Resources are recorded as contracts payable and expensed at the time contracts are awarded. Current period expenses are adjusted for contract refunds or over appropriations when received.

Board designated net assets - From time to time, the Board of Directors designates a portion of unrestricted net assets for various short-term projects.

Cash and cash equivalents - For purposes of the statement of cash flows, cash and cash equivalents consist primarily of deposits in a money market account and investments with original maturities of 90 days or less.

Advertising costs - Advertising costs are expensed as incurred.

Accounts Receivable - Accounts receivable represent sponsor fees billings, and current unreimbursed expenses on various contracts. Allowance for doubtful accounts is normally recorded for amounts deemed as uncollectible. The Council on Library and Information Resources has not recorded any amount for the allowance for doubtful accounts because the Council on Library and Information Resources receives funds on a cost reimbursement basis and sponsorship revenues are current.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2010
(Continued)

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies (continued)

Functional allocation of expenses - Costs of the various programs have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Salaries and travel costs have been allocated directly to programs and administration on a time-allocated basis.

Furniture and Equipment - Furniture and equipment are recorded at cost, less accumulated depreciation. Depreciation expense is computed using the straight-line method over the estimated useful lives of the respective assets. Expenditures for maintenance and repairs are charged against income as incurred; betterments which increase the value or materially extend the life of the related assets are capitalized.

Contributions - The Council on Library and Information Resources records grant income as unrestricted, temporarily restricted, or permanently restricted support, depending upon the terms and conditions of the grant.

Fair value of financial instruments - Management estimates that the fair value of all financial instruments at June 30, 2010 does not differ materially from the aggregate carrying values reported in the accompanying statement of financial position due to the short term maturities of those instruments.

Use of estimates - The preparation of financial statements in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles requires management to make estimates and assumptions that affect the reported amounts of assets and liabilities and disclosure of contingent assets and liabilities at the date of the financial statements. Estimates also affect the reported amounts of revenues and expenses during the reporting period. Actual results could differ from those estimates.

NOTE 2 - Furniture and Equipment

Furniture and equipment consist of the following:

Furniture and equipment	\$ 172,288
Less: Accumulated depreciation and amortization	<u>(133,998)</u>
	<u>\$ 38,290</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2010
(Continued)

NOTE 3- Investments

The Council on Library and Information Resources has adopted SFAS No. 124, "Accounting for Certain Investments Held by Not-for-Profit Organizations." Under SFAS No. 124, investments in marketable securities with readily determinable fair values and all investments in debt securities are reported at their fair values in the statement of financial position. Unrealized gains and losses are included in the change in net assets. Investment income and gains restricted by a donor are reported as increases in unrestricted net assets if the restrictions are met (either by passage of time or by use) in the reporting period in which the income and gains are recognized.

Investment return consists of the following at June 30, 2010

	Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	Unrealized Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	<u>Fair Value</u>
Stocks	\$ 25,299	\$ 41,954	72,769
Bonds	-	2,156	-
Corporate fixed income	8,297	301	-
Government securities	2,429	(3,321)	-
Certificates of deposit	-	-	396,301
Mutual funds	<u>151</u>	<u>28,697</u>	<u>309,629</u>
Subtotal	<u>\$ 36,176</u>	<u>\$ 69,787</u>	<u>\$ 778,699</u>
Cash and cash equivalents	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>\$ 1,149,383</u>
Total	<u>\$ 36,176</u>	<u>\$ 69,787</u>	

The following schedule summarizes the investment and cash equivalent return and its classification in the statement of activities for the year ended June 30, 2010:

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	Temporarily <u>Restricted</u>	<u>Total</u>
Interest and dividends	\$ 7,143	\$ 39,128	\$ 46,271
Realized gains (losses)	9,444	26,732	36,176
Unrealized gains (losses)	<u>5,863</u>	<u>63,924</u>	<u>69,787</u>
Total investment return	<u>\$ 22,450</u>	<u>\$ 129,784</u>	<u>\$ 152,234</u>

NOTE 4 - Income Taxes

The Council on Library and Information Resources is exempt from federal income taxes under Section 501(c)(3) of the Internal Revenue Code and applicable regulations of the District of Columbia.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2010

(Continued)

NOTE 5 - Net Assets released from Restrictions

Net assets were released from grantor restrictions by incurring expenses satisfying the restricted purposes or by occurrence of other events specified by grantors.

NOTE 6 - Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council on Library and Information Resources defined contribution retirement annuity program ("the Plan") administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the Plan provide for full and immediate vesting of the Council on Library and Information Resources contributions. The Council on Library and Information Resources contributes 15% of employees' salaries to the Plan each year. The Council on Library and Information Resources contributions were \$137,269 in 2010.

NOTE 7 - Concentrations of Credit Risk

Financial instruments which potentially subject the Council on Library and Information Resources to concentrations of credit risk consist primarily of cash equivalents. At June 30, 2010, the Council on Library and Information Resources held \$1,928,081 in investments. This amount is not insured by the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation. In addition, cash in the bank at June 30, 2010 exceeded FDIC insurance limits by approximately \$355,450.

The Council on Library and Information Resources received \$1,737,000 from one organization which represents 58 % of total revenue.

NOTE 8 - Accounts Receivable

	June 30, <u>2010</u>
Account balances are aged as follows	
Current	\$ 656,489
30 - 60 days	17,812
60 - 90 days	22,027
Over 90 days	-
Less: Allowance for doubtful accounts	<u> -</u>
Total Accounts Receivable	<u>\$ 696,328</u>

NOTE 9 - Commitments

The Council on Library and Information Resources has entered into a noncancelable operating lease agreement for its office space which expires in August, 2018. Rental expense, net of sublease income for the year ending June 30, 2010 was \$233,350. The Council on Library and Information Resources is also leasing a copier under a capital lease. This lease will expire in January 2015.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2010

(Continued)

NOTE 9 - Commitments (continued)

Future minimum lease payments under all leases with initial remaining noncancelable lease terms in excess of one year are as follows:

Period Ending June 30, _____	Capital Lease	Operating Leases
2011	\$ 1,944	\$ 233,560
2012	1,944	258,873
2013	1,944	267,934
2014	1,944	277,312
2015 and beyond	1,134	1,763,759
Total minimum lease payments	\$ 8,910	\$ <u>2,801,438</u>
Less: Amount representing interest. Present value of net minimum lease payments	_____	_____
	\$ <u>8,910</u>	

NOTE 10 - Board Designated Net Assets Funds

The Board of Directors voted to designate net assets of \$400,000 for operating reserves.

NOTE 11 - Fair Value of Financial Instruments

The carrying amounts reflected in the balance sheets for cash, cash equivalents, loans and notes payable approximate the respective fair values due to the short maturities of those instruments. SFAS 157 requires a fair value hierarchy to be used to prioritize valuation inputs into three levels:

Level 1 – Quoted prices (unadjusted) in active markets for identical assets or liabilities.

Level 2 – Observable inputs other than the quoted prices included in Level 1.

Level 3 – Unobservable inputs.

Fair values of assets and liabilities measured on a nonrecurring basis at June 30, 2010 are as follows:

Description	Fair Value	(Level 1)	(Level 2)	(Level 3)	(Losses)
Long-lived assets held for sale	\$ 778,699	—	\$ 778,699	\$ -	-

Long-lived assets have been valued using a market approach. The values were determined using market prices of similar long-lived assets.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2010

(Concluded)

NOTE 12 – Transfer of Assets

In July 2009, the Digital Library Federation ceased to do business and transferred its remaining net assets to the Council on Library and Information Resources. At the time of transfer, the Council on Library and Information resources did not provide any consideration in exchange for the net assets received. There was no stipulation as to how the funds should be used by the Council, therefore, the Council considers the funds unrestricted. The amount of funds transferred to the Council in July 2009 was \$516,398 which represents fair value.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES
SCHEDULE OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES
For The Year Ended June 30, 2010

	<u>The Next Scholar</u>	<u>Cyber Infrastructure</u>	<u>Leadership</u>	<u>Preservation</u>	<u>Digital Library</u>	<u>Other</u>	<u>International Developments</u>	<u>Total Program</u>
Employee costs	\$252,399	\$112,904	\$50,962	\$424,566	\$64,054	\$745	\$	\$905,630
Professional Services and contracts	67,898	42,657	500	77,159	77,174	17,875		283,263
Fellowships, scholarships and interns	361,545		10,000					371,545
Grants	4,039,858							4,039,858
Communications	20,886	2,611	19,658	108	3,673	98		47,034
Travel and meetings	249,269	65,869	25,957	15,287	113,948	79,888	93,403	643,621
Publications	1,133			9,745	2,038	12,768		25,684
Office operations	17,400	3,301	193	5,943	1,096	17,523	26	45,482
Total	<u>\$5,010,388</u>	<u>\$227,342</u>	<u>\$107,270</u>	<u>\$532,808</u>	<u>\$261,983</u>	<u>\$128,897</u>	<u>\$93,429</u>	<u>\$6,362,117</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES
SCHEDULE OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES
For The Year Ended June 30, 2010

	<u>Total Program</u>	<u>Administration</u>	<u>Total</u>
Employee costs	\$905,630	\$425,455	\$1,331,085
Professional Services and contracts	283,263	116,092	399,355
Fellowships, scholarships and interns	371,545	5,500	377,045
Grants	4,039,858	-	4,039,858
Communications	47,034	19,869	66,903
Travel and meetings	643,621	61,762	705,383
Publications	25,684	9,473	35,157
Office operations	<u>45,482</u>	<u>305,418</u>	<u>350,900</u>
Total	<u>\$6,362,117</u>	<u>\$943,569</u>	<u>\$7,305,686</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

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